

The Impact of Yoga creating Excellence in Career Development

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ABSTRACT

Yoga, is an ancient method of controlling emotional imbalances, physical and mental disturbances. It helps in contemporary workplace, especially in developing employee's career. Yoga is a powerful tool for enhancing career development and maintaining excellence in workplace. This abstract explores the impact of yoga on individual's career development in all dimensions.

Yoga promotes physical and mental health by cultivating strength, flexibility and courage for accepting professional challenges which is very importance in this competitive world.

Yoga assist in developing the employees focus, concentration and decision making. It also enhances in achieving the organizational goals. Regular practice of yoga helps in developing higher level thinking, getting clarity and navigating complex professional challenges. It also helps professional development as well as personal development for individual and increasing good leadership qualities and innovative ideas. It creates positive work environment which leads to high productivity in the organization. This study helps in understanding how yoga beneficial to the corporate sector in maintaining the positive work environment in critical situation.

Moreover, it pivots work life balance, job satisfaction inner peace which leads individual for better position to pursue their career goals with enthusiasm and effectiveness.

Keywords: *Emotional Balance, Leadership, Decision-Making, Work Life balance, Job satisfaction and contemporary workplace.*

INTRODUCTION

In this competitive professional challenges, individuals are increasing to holistic practices to enhance their career path and overall well-being. Among these practices, yoga stands out as a tool to promote physical and mental fitness for emotional balances and mental clarity in contemporary workplace. Yoga is originated from ancient India which incorporates rich tradition of asanas, which harmonises the mind, body and spirit. The integration of yoga and career development programs has gained insightful impact on various aspects of career advancement.

Yoga practices contributes to career development by nurturing physical and mental health, enhancing cognitive abilities and emotional intelligence and refining leadership qualities. In modern approaches yoga assist in achieving excellence in the workplace. Yoga helps in development of positive organisational culture and climate. It also incorporates in setting professional goals to the individual for sustainable success and personal growth.

Need and Scope of the study:

The need of the study is that Yoga promotes emotional intelligence by nurturing self-awareness, empathy, and effective communication which helps in building positive environment and managing disputes and creating healthy work environment.

The scope of yoga's impact on career development is widespread, encircling physical health, mental well-being, emotional intelligence, leadership development, work-life balance, and organizational culture. These benefit can considerably develop professional effectiveness, job satisfaction and overall career achievements in contemporary workplace.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To analyse the impact of yoga in improving emotional intelligence and stress management to workplace pressures.
2. To analyse the relation between yoga practice and leadership qualities.

3. To study how integrating yoga into corporate wellness programmes which impact on employee morale and productivity.

Research Methodology

This is totally based on descriptive analysis and on systematic collection of secondary data from different sources. The information will be providing a comprehensive view of the impact of yoga on career development focusing on important dimensions.

Review of Literature:

1. **Nidhi Chaudhry et.al** this expresses that pioneering base for further observational and interventional studies to develop measures and personalized protocols for PE. **In Yoga perspective on personal excellence and well-being.**
2. ***Ingunn Hagen** The purpose of this article is to explore how yoga may be a tool for increased wellbeing and stress management at work and in everyday life. The impact of yoga on occupational stress and wellbeing: exploring practitioners' experiences*
3. *Mr. Gireesan EM This paper examines the impact of spiritual practices on the quality of work life of IT employees in Ernakulam district, Kerala. **Spiritual Practices in the Workplace and Its Impact on Quality of Work Life among IT Employees with Special Reference To Ernamakulam District.***

Ch Sri Sai Ratna In this purpose a study has been conducted to determine the impact of yoga practices on worklife balance of women managers in selective organisations in Visakhapatnam city **IMPACT OF YOGA PRACTICE ON WORK-LIFE BALANCE OF WOMEN MANAGERS – A STUDY IN SELECTIVE ORGANISATIONS**

Findings

- The physiological benefits of yoga that contribute to improve job performance and reduced Labour turnover.
- The Yoga assist in professional development such as good leadership qualities and concentration and decision making abilities.

- The Yoga helps in developing emotional intelligence and stress management skills.

Conclusion

This study concludes with a summary of findings and implications of yoga in corporate wellness programmes leads to professional development and sustainable career success and effectiveness in contemporary workplace.

References:

- Yoga perspective on personal excellence and well-being (2023)
- Author links open overlay panel - Nidhi Chaudhry ^a, Rudra B. Bhandari ^a, Vaishali Gaur ^b
- The impact of yoga on occupational stress and wellbeing: exploring practitioners' experiences, Ingunn Hagen.
- Spiritual Practices in the Workplace and Its Impact on Quality of Work Life among IT Employees with Special Reference To Ernamakulam District Mr. Gireesan EM
- IMPACT OF YOGA PRACTICE ON WORK-LIFE BALANCE OF WOMEN MANAGERS – A STUDY IN SELECTIVE ORGANISATIONS Ch Sri Sai Ratna